

Anti-psoriatic effects of topical ezetimibe on imiquimod-induced psoriasis mouse model

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Received 27 September 2025 ♦ Accepted 14 December 2025 ♦ Published 26 January 2026

Citation: Al-Athari AJH, Shihab EM, Aldhalmi AK, AlBairmani RJH, Shahooth SS (2026) Anti-psoriatic effects of topical ezetimibe on imiquimod-induced psoriasis mouse model. *Pharmacia* 73: 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e173266>

Abstract

Objective: This work aims to estimate the effectiveness of topically administered ezetimibe on an imiquimod-evoked psoriasis-like mouse model. **Methods:** Twenty-four albino mice were assorted equally into four groups (6 animals in every group), comprising controls, induction, calcipotriol 0.05% (standard drug), and ezetimibe 3%. The topical medications were administered for 7 successive days. Disease intensity scores, histomorphological alterations, and biochemical mediators of inflammation, angiogenesis, and oxidative stress were evaluated. **Results:** Topical ezetimibe significantly ameliorated cumulative Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) grades and histological changes versus the induction (imiquimod) group. It significantly deregulated the generation of inflammatory signaling molecules, specifically IL-17A, IL-23, and TNF- α , together with enhancing the anti-inflammatory component IL-10. This finding was also paralleled by a remarkable decrement in angiogenic indices like vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), reduction of oxidative stress indices such as malondialdehyde (MDA), and strengthening of the actions of the antioxidative molecules superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT). **Conclusion:** Ezetimibe demonstrates remarkable anti-psoriatic activity, as proved by the suppression of inflammatory, angiogenic, and oxidative measures.

Keywords

ezetimibe, imiquimod model, inflammation, oxidative stress, psoriasis

Introduction

Psoriasis is a lifelong, immune-related/autoinflammatory dermatosis with complex pathogenesis and a relapsing-remitting course that may last a lifetime. Although no cure exists, the combined interrelation of hereditary susceptibility, environmental triggers, and immunological imbalance has been demonstrated to be vital in disease initiation (Rendon and Schäkel 2019; Ali et al. 2025a).

Psoriasis is correlated with epidermal hyperproliferation and inflammatory skin lesions, which can also affect joints, as in psoriatic arthritis. The prevalence of the disease varies by season and also between men and women throughout the world, affecting about 2–4% of the population in all age groups (Parisi et al. 2020; Bu et al. 2022). The clinical picture of psoriasis usually finds red plaques with silvery-white flaky scales of various sizes—often affecting the knees, sacral region, scalp area, buttocks, and

elbows—although pustular aggravated eruptions can also occur on palms and soles or may universally spread over skin (Alzeer et al. 2022; ALHamdi and ALHamdi 2023). The Koebner phenomenon also takes place in psoriatic inflammation, as well as other dermal diseases like flat warts and hair graying (Ji and Liu 2019; Ali et al. 2025b; Sharquie et al. 2005)

Aside from cutaneous lesions, psoriasis is recently regarded to be a systemic ailment that is related to several comorbidities, including obesity, diabetic dermopathy, dyslipidemia, ulcerative colitis, and renal dysfunction (Oliveira Mde et al. 2015; Ryan and Kirby 2015). Among these, metabolic hyperlipidemia is an important factor that complicates psoriasis (Luo et al. 2023). Increased LDL cholesterol and oxidized lipids might enhance the proliferation of keratinocytes, stimulate dendritic cell activity, and activate multiple pro-inflammatory pathways, including STAT3, NF- κ B, and MAPK network (Shih et al. 2020; Su et al. 2023). This culminates in an amplification loop that connects metabolic perturbations with systemic as well as cutaneous inflammation and the increased production of many mediators, comprising IL-6, TNF- α , IL-17, and IL-23 (Menter et al. 2021; Wang 2023). Accordingly, psoriasis is increasingly recognized as an underlying inflammatory process linked to metabolic imbalances, rather than a simple dermatosis (Wu et al. 2022).

Topical application of a TLR-7 stimulator, imiquimod, induces psoriasis-like skin lesions if repeatedly administered to mice (Hussein et al. 2020; Khaleel et al. 2024). Also, psoriatic inflammation could manifest itself not only at the administration sites but also in surrounding areas that had previously been uninvolved (Ridha-Salman et al. 2024a). This simple and repeatable approach may be employed to evaluate new therapies or drugs (Hanna et al. 2016).

Ezetimibe is a classical lipid-modulating medication and functions selectively via hampering the Niemann-Pick C1-like 1 (NPC1L1) protein implicated in cholesterol uptake (Gómez Garre et al. 2009). Ezetimibe reduces liver cholesterol input, stimulates abundance of the LDL receptor, and increases circulating LDL removal by reducing absorption of bile and dietary cholesterol. It is of clinical interest in the treatment of hypercholesterolemia and atherosclerotic events as monotherapy or in combination with statins (Pandor et al. 2009; Phan et al. 2012; Arsenaault et al. 2018; Niedzielski et al. 2020). Ezetimibe additionally acts via enhancement of the Nrf2/HO-1 antioxidant axis, suppression of lipid peroxidation, and protection from ROS-mediated damage in keratinocytes, which is a significant factor triggering epidermal hyperproliferation and immunological stimulation, characteristic of inflammatory skin diseases (Chiricozzi et al. 2018). It additionally inhibits dendritic cell function and Th17 differentiation, which may make it possible to downregulate the psoriatic IL-23/IL-17 circuit (Moon et al. 2022).

Meanwhile, ezetimibe has several modes of action in psoriasis besides its lipid-regulating action. It could interfere with important drivers of psoriatic inflammation, especially IL-1 β , IL-18, TNF- α , and macrophage

migration, alongside monocyte chemoattractant protein 1 (MCP-1)-mediated chemoattraction giving rise to impaired trafficking of immune cells to sites of inflammation (Tobaru et al. 2013; Cannon et al. 2015). The impact of ezetimibe on some inflammatory markers has also been studied. It was reported that ezetimibe suppressed plaque formation, macrophage accumulation, and chemoattractant release, such as MCP-1 and TNF- α (Tie et al. 2015; Cho et al. 2020). Besides, other reports suggest that ezetimibe and simvastatin combined could be efficient in the management of autoimmune alopecia totalis and alopecia universalis, indicating a potential therapeutic value for resistant forms of alopecia areata (Choi et al. 2017). This compound also had protective effects in IL-1 β -exaggerated matrix collagen degradation of murine chondrocytes by regulating NF- κ B and Nrf2/Nr 197, but further studies are required to evaluate its activity as a matrix metalloproteinase inhibitor (Weng et al. 2022). In a similar manner, ezetimibe exhibited inhibitory effects against the acetic acid-challenged ulcerative colitis through down-regulating inflammatory and oxidant markers (Mostafa and Abdel-Rahman 2023). Apoptotic markers, including caspase-1, caspase-3, and p-ASK1, as well as the Bax/Bcl2 ratio, were reduced by ezetimibe, while inflammatory mediators, including IL-18 and IL-1 β , were reduced (Fathy et al. 2024).

Therefore, the current experiment has been designed to determine the mitigative role of topical ezetimibe in an imiquimod-evoked psoriasiform dermatitis murine model. Through the repurposing of a widely used cholesterol-lowering drug with known anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, this research aims to explore an innovative therapeutic approach that addresses the metabolic-inflammatory crosstalk integral to psoriasis.

Materials and methods

Drugs and reagents

Imiquimod 5% cream was a kind offer from MEDA Pharmaceutical Industry, Sweden, while ezetimibe powder was donated by PharmaCompass, Germany. Calcipotriol (Daivonex) 0.005% ointment was supplied by Leo Pharma, Denmark, whereas petroleum jelly was obtained from Julphar Gulf Pharmaceutical Industries, UAE. The ezetimibe topical preparations used in this study were prepared using chemicals provided by certified pharmaceutical companies.

Formulation of ezetimibe ointment

The ointment base was prepared using the appropriate weight of an oleaginous base. A porcelain chamber was mounted on a heated bath. Molten paraffin wax was then mixed with lanolin alcohol and white soft paraffin (Habbas et al. 2025). In the subsequent step, the levigation method was used to gently mix 3 g of powdered ezetimibe with an adequate quantity of Vaseline base until a clear, homoge-

neous ointment weighing 100 g was obtained (Hussein et al. 2025). Thereafter, sterile, clean plastic containers were used to store the ezetimibe ointment. The containers were tightly sealed and preserved at appropriate temperature.

Experimental protocol

The project for educational investigation was authorized by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Al-Esraa University, Faculty of Pharmacy. The research was conducted between February 2025 and June 2025. Mice were provided by the Center for Biomedical Investigation, Kufa University. The mice were 9–12 weeks of age and averaged 28 to 35 g. Rodents were housed at a constant temperature of 24 ± 2 °C and had full usage of water, wheat, and minerals. To minimize licking and physical contact, three animals from each group were maintained in new plastic germ-free cages. Twenty-four male Swiss albino mice were enrolled in the existing trial and allocated randomly into four categories (6 animals each).

All mice had their dorsal hair stripped 1 day before the study using a hand razor and then with depilatory cream to remove any remaining hair. About 1 cc of shaving cream was also placed and left in contact with the dorsal skin for a few minutes to facilitate hair removal. The soaked cream was gently washed away with warm water without causing any irritation. This method is widely used in mouse skin disease models and has no apparent skin damage when the treatment period was fast (Naji et al. 2022; Almudaris and Gatea 2024; AlBairmani et al. 2025). No rats demonstrated erythema, scratches, or gross irritants prior to imiquimod application.

The mice were arranged into 4 main groups:

- **Control group:** comprised untreated normal animals.
- **Imiquimod/induction group:** got 62.5 mg of imiquimod 5% cream followed by 62.5 mg of Vaseline 2 hours later, once a day for 7 days (Van Der Fits et al. 2009).
- **Calcipotriol group:** obtained 62.5 mg of imiquimod 5% cream, followed by calcipotriol 0.005% ointment applied twice daily, starting 2 hours after imiquimod administration, for 7 successive days (Ridha-Salman et al. 2024b).
- **Ezetimibe group:** Animals were given 62.5 mg of 5% imiquimod, followed 2 hours later by 3% ezetimibe ointment, applied twice daily for 7 days (Shalal et al. 2025). The rodents were killed after the completion of the experimental procedures with a mixture of ketamine and xylazine (Pierozan et al. 2017; Mohsin et al. 2020), and skin was obtained for histological and biochemical studies.

Evaluating severity of symptoms in psoriatic-like inflammation

PASI, a parameter of psoriatic development, was determined by measuring the dorsal skin fold thickness, and erythema and desquamation in this region were recorded

daily. Each parameter was graded from 0 to 4 (where 0 = none; 1 = mild; 2 = moderate; 3 = marked; and 4 = very marked) during the experimentation period (Khorshed and Raghif 2024). The sum of erythema/redness, scaling, and cutaneous thickness (scores 0 to 12) was used to compute the cumulative PASI score (Van Der Fits et al. 2009; Jabeen et al. 2020).

Processing of skin specimens

The dorsal skins were excised from the mice after euthanasia. A portion of the harvested skin tissue was swiftly repaired in 10% NBF for histopathological evaluation, and the rest was quickly frozen for biochemical marker investigation.

Preparation of cutaneous tissue homogenates

Dorsal skin (1 g) was stored in 9 ml of phosphate buffer at pH 7.2. The tissue extracts were ground up in a blender and separated at 5,000 rpm for 16 min under cooling conditions. The supernatants were poured into microvessels and kept at -80 to -20 °C (Shihab et al. 2025).

Histopathological estimation

Skin tissues dehydrated in ascending alcohol (70–100%) and cleared in xylol were isolated. The tissues were then placed into paraffin wax (55–60 °C) to solidify. Four- to 5- μ m-thick sections were positioned on egg albumin-coated slides and flattened out by floating the slides on a warm water bath (Abbod et al. 2014). Sections were fully air-dried and treated with hematoxylin and eosin to visualize cytoplasmic and extracellular matrix components. Slides were dehydrated and cleared with xylol and mounted for microscopic observation. This technique provided high-resolution analysis of cell morphology, epidermal and dermal structure, and pathological changes resulting from experimental treatments.

Grading of psoriatic skin alterations

Severity of histopathological skin changes in experimental groups of animals was assessed using Baker's evaluation criteria on a scale from 0 to 10. The average scores of all sections were determined from unbiased readings (Baker and Fry 1992).

Estimation of inflammation-linked and angiogenic parameters

The concentrations of TNF- α , IL-10, IL-17, IL-23, and VEGF in homogenized skins are determined by an ELISA test based on the manufacturers' instructions. Briefly, 96-well plates were coated with specific anti-cytokine antibodies. Specimens and reference materials were dispensed to the microplate cavities, allowing immobilized antibodies to bind TNF- α , IL-10, IL-17, IL-23, and VEGF present in the samples. Optical density values were measured spectro-pho-

tometrically and correlated with biomarker concentrations using standard curves (Abdulbari et al. 2025). After a second washing step, tetramethylbenzidine substrate was added, and the resulting color reaction indicated the level of bound cytokines. The reaction was stopped, producing a distinct color transition from blue to yellow, and absorbance readings were logged at 450 nm (Abbas et al. 2022; Motib and Idan 2025).

Estimating oxidative damage-associated bio-indicators

Determination of MDA amounts

Thiobarbituric acid-reactive substances (TBARS) had been quantified with the use of a spectrophotometer to estimate malondialdehyde (MDA) formation in tissue. An appropriate volume of skin homogenates were merged with 3 mL of 1% H_3PO_4 and 1 mL of 0.6% thiobarbituric acid (TBA), and the combination has been transferred to a test tube. The contents were incubated in a thermostatically controlled water bath for approximately 30 min. Absorbance has been measured spectrophotometrically at 535 nm. Lipid peroxide concentrations were quantified using the TBARS method, and results were reflected as nmol/g tissue (Mihara and Uchiyama 1978).

Assessment of SOD and CAT levels

SOD value was determined using the nitroblue tetrazolium (NBT) procedure based on the xanthine-xanthine oxidoreductase system, where one unit corresponded to the content of enzyme necessary to achieve 50% inhibition of NBT reduction. Catalase value was estimated spectrophotometrically at 374 nm using hydrogen peroxide as the substrate and was expressed as KU/L (Hadwan and Abed 2016).

Results

Effects of calcipotriol and ezetimibe on severity scores of psoriatic lesions

The imiquimod induction group developed marked psoriatic features, including erythema, scaling, and increased dorsal skin thickness, with remarkably greater total PASI and Baker's grades versus the controls ($p < 0.05$). Mice treated with either calcipotriol or ezetimibe exhibited significant reductions in macroscopic psoriatic manifestations, along with markedly lower cumulative PASI and Baker's scores ($p < 0.05$) versus the imiquimod model group, as apparent in Figs 1, 2.

Impact of calcipotriol and ezetimibe on inflammatory measures

The imiquimod induction group showed significantly increased skin levels of inflammation-associated elements,

Figure 1. A. Impact of calcipotriol and ezetimibe on cumulative PASI scores; **B.** Impact of calcipotriol and ezetimibe on Baker's scores. Outcomes are expressed as mean \pm SD; * = substantial change ($p < 0.05$) vs. non-treated controls; ** = substantial change ($p < 0.05$) vs. induction/model group.

namely TNF- α , IL-17A, and IL-23, along with reduced quantities of IL-10 opposed with the baseline controls ($p < 0.05$). In contrast, the ezetimibe and calcipotriol groups demonstrated remarkably declined output of TNF- α , IL-17A, and IL-23, paired with increased IL-10 concentrations relative to the imiquimod/induction group ($p < 0.05$), as detailed in Fig. 3.

Impact of calcipotriol and ezetimibe on angiogenic measures

The model/imiquimod group showed profoundly upregulated cutaneous levels of VEGF contrasted to the normal controls ($p < 0.05$). In contrast, both the calcipotriol-treated and ezetimibe-treated groups exhibited markedly reduced VEGF levels if matched to the model/imiquimod group ($p < 0.05$). Notably, the ezetimibe group manifested meaningfully lower VEGF levels against the model/induction group, as illustrated in Fig. 4.

Impact of calcipotriol and ezetimibe on oxidative biomarkers

The model/imiquimod group demonstrated markedly increased production of the oxidative marker MDA, along with reduced activities of detoxifying enzymes, notably SOD and CAT, in skin tissue versus the non-treated controls ($p < 0.05$). Both the calcipotriol and ezetimibe inter-

Figure 2. Macroscopic images of dorsal skin from each group after completion of the study.

Figure 3. Influence of calcipotriol and ezetimibe on inflammation-associated signaling molecules (TNF- α , IL-10, IL-17A, and IL-23). Findings were reflected as mean \pm SD; * points to notable differences ($p < 0.05$) from the non-treated controls, and # points to notable differences ($p < 0.05$) from the induction/model group.

Figure 4. Impact of calcipotriol and ezetimibe on the angiogenesis biomarker VEGF. Findings were reflected as mean \pm SD; *points to remarkable changes ($p < 0.05$) from the non-treated controls, ** points to notable differences ($p < 0.05$) from the model/induction group, and # points to notable differences ($p < 0.05$) from the calcipotriol group.

vention groups displayed remarkably reduced MDA levels and markedly increased SOD and CAT activities in relation to the model/imiquimod group ($p < 0.05$), as shown in Fig. 5.

Impact of calcipotriol and ezetimibe on cutaneous histopathological changes

Histopathological examination revealed that the control group exhibited normal dermal and epidermal architecture (Fig. 6). On the other hand, induced imiquimod treatment resulted in marked psoriatic histopathological features such as severe lymphocytic inflammatory infiltration, Munro abscess formation, hyperkeratotic changes, prominent rete ridges and epidermal thickening (acanthosis), and congestion compared with the control index (Fig. 6).

Figure 5. Influence of calcipotriol and ezetimibe on oxidative components (MDA, SOD, and CAT). Findings were reflected as mean \pm SD. * points to meaningful variations ($p < 0.05$) from the control group, and ** points to meaningful variations ($p < 0.05$) from the model/induction group. While the results for SOD were shown as (U/g protein), the statistics for MDA and CAT actions were shown as (nmol per gram).

Figure 6. **A.** Non-treated control group showing normal cutaneous thickness (green arrow), absence of inflammation (blue arrow), no congestion (red arrow), and lack of hyperkeratosis (yellow bar); **B.** Induction group showing prominent rete ridges (yellow bar), pronounced Munro abscesses (red arrow) (H&E 40 \times), marked hyperkeratotic changes (blue arrow), extensive inflammatory cell infiltration (black bar), and severe congestion (green arrow) (H&E 10 \times); **C.** Calcipotriol group showing minimal psoriatic inflammation (yellow bar), mild rete ridge elongation (blue bar), minor acanthotic changes (green bar), and mild hyperkeratotic plaques (red bar) (H&E 10 \times); **D.** Ezetimibe-treated group showing relatively mild hyperkeratotic alterations (blue arrow), reduced epidermal thickness (green bar), mild lymphocytic infiltration (red arrow), and slight rete peg elongation (yellow arrow) (H&E 10 \times).

However, topical calcipotriol 0.05% and ezetimibe 3% provided significant improvement when compared to the group inducing partial or complete regression of psoriatic histopathological changes. Accordingly, skin sections from mice in the calcipotriol group exhibited minor showed mild inflammation, slight rete ridge elongation, mild acanthotic changes, and modest hyperkeratotic plaques (Fig. 6). In comparison, mice in the ezetimibe group exhibited relatively mild hyperkeratosis, reduced cutaneous thicknesses, modest rete peg elongations, mild lymphocytic infiltrations, and absence of congestions (Fig. 6).

Discussion

The current study showed that topical ezetimibe exerted a marked anti-psoriatic effect in imiquimod-treated mice, as demonstrated by clinical, histopathological, and biochemical endpoints. Treatments were associated with a dramatic reduction in cumulative PASI scores, correction of cutaneous appearance, a decrease in pro-inflammatory cytokine expression and angiogenesis, as well as a remarkable enhancement of antioxidant defenses. These findings provide strong evidence that the lipid-lowering agent ezetimibe exhibits pleiotropic effects that could potentially be exploited for psoriasis therapy.

Imiquimod-provoked psoriatic dermatitis closely resembles the human disease, exhibiting redness, scaling and flaking, acanthosis and thickening, hyperkeratosis, parakeratosis, and characteristic histological changes, including Munro's abscesses, hyperkeratosis, and parakeratosis. Research has shown that erythema reflects the extent of cutaneous blood vessel dilation, which is thought to be elicited by a combination of mediators, including histamine and nitric oxide, produced by various skin cells (Abbas et al. 2024; Khafaji et al. 2024; Salman et al. 2024a). Skin induration is caused by keratinocytic proliferation elicited through pro-inflammatory cytokines, whereas improper keratinocytic differentiation leads to the formation of whitish-gray scales (Abbas et al. 2023; Hasan and Gatea 2024; Salman et al. 2024b).

Clinically, mice treated topically with ezetimibe showed pronounced reductions in overall PASI scores, whereas no improvement was documented in mice treated with imiquimod alone. These macroscopic effects were comparable to those induced by calcipotriol, a gold-standard topical therapy. The clinical improvement was confirmed histologically, showing that ezetimibe reduced epidermal hyperplasia and the formation of Munro's abscesses, along with decreased dermal infiltration of inflammatory cells. Those above outcomes align with findings reported by Tie et al. (2015), to lower inflammatory cell accumulation and tissue remodeling in atherosclerotic plaques, indicating effects beyond the vascular wall that might also be relevant for skin manifestation (Tie et al. 2015).

The anti-inflammatory action of ezetimibe was the most pronounced among its immunomodulatory features in this study. TNF- α , IL-17A, and IL-23, being core effectors in the activation and control of the IL-23/Th17 route, were significantly suppressed by ezetimibe treatment. IL-23 provides strong differentiation and stabilization signals for Th17 cells, thereby excessive IL-17 secretion generating keratinocyte proliferation and neutrophil recruitment, respectively (Girolomoni et al. 2017; Abbas et al. 2025b). By abrogating this axis, ezetimibe may work directly on the immunopathogenic arm that maintains psoriasiform dermatitis. Our results are consistent with earlier reports that ezetimibe inhibits the stimulation of dendritic cells and Th17 maturation in experimental studies (Moon et al. 2022; Ju et al. 2024), alongside reducing TNF- α , IL-17, and IL-1 β expressions in experimental models of UC (Jaafar and Abu-Raghif 2023b; Jaafar and Abu-Raghif 2024). Concomitantly, ezetimibe has been found to enhance endothelial function and decrease inflammatory markers as well as disease progression in both clinical and preclinical models of rheumatoid arthritis (Mäki-Petäjä et al. 2007; Barbosa et al. 2017). In addition, ezetimibe enhanced IL-10 expression in the current study, an immunomodulatory cytokine essential for suppressing excessive Th1 and Th17 responses and facilitating immune tolerance regulation (Hayashi et al. 2016; Ridha-Salman et al. 2024a). This is in agreement with clinical evidence showing increased IL-10 and reduced pro-inflammatory mediators after treatment of metabolic syndrome patients with ezetimibe (Liu et al. 2013; Jackowska et al. 2019). Altogether, it is widely implied that ezetimibe has strong immunomodulation capacity, potentially shifting immune responses from a pro-inflammatory direction to a regulatory one (Woźniak et al. 2023).

An additional interesting finding was the VEGF, which has been identified to critically contribute to angiogenesis, wound repair, and cancer development (Khaleel et al. 2025; Thammer et al. 2025). VEGF expression was highly decreased in ezetimibe-treated mice. Angiogenesis is another histopathological characteristic of psoriatic plaques, and it enhances leukocyte infiltration as well as prolongation of chronicity (Heidenreich et al. 2009; Henno et al. 2009). Augmented abundance of VEGF are linked to more severe disease and resistance to treatment (Khorsheed et al. 2024). In this work, ezetimibe significantly inhibited VEGF generation in a sugar-induced model and thus might have a therapeutic effect via inhibition of dermal neovascularization. This finding is in line with previous findings demonstrating an inhibition of vascular proliferation and remodeling by ezetimibe in models of cardiovascular disease and endometriosis (Li et al. 2018; Tapdıgova et al. 2022). Owing to its antiangiogenic capacities (Solomon et al. 2009; Ahmed et al. 2023), ezetimibe represents a mode of action not usually seen with classic topical treatments like calcipotriol.

Oxidative stress is another feature of psoriasis pathogenesis (Dobrică et al. 2022). Therefore, we also assessed parameters of oxidative stress to elucidate the possible antioxidant effects of ezetimibe. MDA was used to determine the status of lipid peroxidation, while SOD and CAT were regarded as the important components in the endogenous antioxidant protection system in numerous organs (Al-Oudah et al. 2024; Jaafar et al. 2025; Raheem et al. 2025). The effect of the imiquimod model on lipid peroxidation as measured by MDA and antioxidant enzyme (SOD, CAT) activity was significantly higher (Abbas et al. 2025a; Ali et al. 2025a). These changes are supported by clinical findings, as it has been reported that psoriasis individuals exhibited elevated oxidative damage and weakened antioxidant capacity that could lead to keratinocyte proliferation and DNA damage (Lin and Huang 2016; Dobrică et al. 2022). In the current investigation, ezetimibe therapy resulted in an improvement of SOD and CAT activities, a decrease in MDA concentration, and redox equilibrium accompanied by normalization. Nrf2/HO-1 is a well-known pathway that had previously been demonstrated to be activated by ezetimibe and to contribute to antioxidant defenses (Chen et al. 2024; Fathy et al. 2024) and protect keratinocytes or chondrocytes from ROS-sensitive apoptosis upon different noxious evasions (Weng et al. 2022; Lee et al. 2025; Shallal et al. 2025). Therefore, the antioxidative effects seen here are in line with published data and reinforce the notion that ezetimibe might be of benefit in inflammatory diseases with oxidative stress (Jaafar and Abu-Raghif 2023a; Shallal et al. 2025).

With respect to lipid metabolism, the relevance of psoriasis is increasingly coming into focus. Aberrant lipids and oxidized LDL are potent activators of dendritic cells, augmenting NF- κ B signaling and contributing to systemic and cutaneous inflammation (Ikeda et al. 2022; Luo et al. 2023). Metabolic complications, notably obesity, heart problems, and diabetes, are common in psoriatic participants (Takeshita et al. 2017; Hassan et al. 2025; Luty et al. 2025). By blocking intestinal NPC1L1-dependent cholesterol uptake, ezetimibe lowers circulating LDL and inhibits lipid-induced inflammatory responses (Simon et al. 2016; Niedzielski et al. 2020). In view of this, the current investigation shines light on an important consideration in treatment: ezetimibe not only blocks metabolic but also immunologic aspects of psoriasis. This dual effect may be effective as a repurposed therapeutic candidate, especially in patients with coexisting metabolic syndrome or dyslipidemia. Consistent with this notion, Fathy et al. reported on the decrease in expression levels of both IL1 β and IL-18, apoptotic markers, and the increased antioxidant defense process; they strengthened even more its pleiotropic face (Fathy et al. 2024).

The current findings showed that both ezetimibe and calcipotriol mitigated clinical and histological changes. The mechanism of ezetimibe seemed to be, however, broader than that of calcipotriol, since it affected not only angiogenesis and oxidative stress but also immune cytokines. This broad spectrum of actions indicates that eze-

timibe might be useful not only as an alternative topical treatment but also as a co-adjuvant for conventional pharmacological treatments.

Calcipotriol was chosen as the positive control treatment because it is well established to influence keratinocytic multiplication and differentiation in psoriasis and, compared with the extended exposure of topically administered corticosteroids, has fewer undesirable effects (Kubin et al. 2016; Abbas et al. 2025a; Farooq Ali et al. 2025). However, skin irritation and calcium metabolism abnormalities were described in some people treated with calcipotriol (Tiberio et al. 2009; Ridha-Salman et al. 2024b), and ezetimibe may be a more well-tolerated option with beneficial metabolic effects, whereas ezetimibe may represent a safer and metabolically favorable alternative.

The overall data suggest that ezetimibe as a topical treatment for psoriasis is possible and would seem to be an attractive approach. Topical administration reduces the systemic bioavailability and unwanted lipid-lowering effects, but local use of its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties is not challenged or limited. Additional research is necessary to optimize formulation, delineate dermal pharmacokinetics, and assess long-term human efficacy and safety. Clinical trials will be required to determine if this benefit observed in the current preclinical model translates into clinically significant therapies for patients with psoriasis, especially those with metabolic comorbidities.

Limitations

There are certain drawbacks to this study, despite the evidence favoring the utility of ezetimibe therapy being compelling. An obvious shortcoming of this study is that the number of animals was rather small, which had an impact on statistical power and generalizability. Furthermore, the model of imiquimod application is extensively validated, but it is an acute inflammatory status that does not fully reproduce the relapsing–remitting progress in human psoriasis.

A further drawback of the current trial is the absence of dose-dependent analysis. Methods Testing of 3% topical ezetimibe was selected for the throughput-extricated study, which does not allow for distinguishing dose-related effects, possible toxicities, and optimal treatment duration. The examination of a wider range of dose concentrations, as well as furthering the span of the duration of treatment, will provide greater insights into safety and efficacy profiling. Furthermore, ezetimibe is a medication for oral use; whether topical application to the skin can achieve cutaneous penetration, local retention, and systemic absorption of this agent has not yet been established. Hence, forthcoming studies must also focus on pharmacokinetics and tissue-selective distribution of ezetimibe following topical application. Additionally, despite evaluation of inflammatory, oxidative, and angiogenic markers, specific molecular and immunohistochemical analyses were not carried out to clarify key signaling pathways mediated by topical application of ezetimibe (espe-

cially NF- κ B, STAT3, MAPK, and Nrf2), which should be considered in future studies through Western blot or PCR. Future studies may also warrant examining a third treatment arm of combined topical ezetimibe and calcipotriol to determine whether there may be synergistic or additive effects on psoriatic severity and inflammatory markers. Finally, prolonged observational investigations are warranted to estimate the duration of pharmacological actions, prevention of relapse, and safety.

Conclusion

The current results show that ezetimibe has substantial therapeutic effects in the murine psoriasiform dermatitis model via its anti-inflammatory, antioxidative, and anti-angiogenic activities. Ezetimibe simultaneously targets immunological and metabolic-inflammatory pathways, making it a promising candidate for drug repurposing as a novel anti-psoriatic therapy. Future studies should further explore long-lasting efficacy, pharmacokinetics, and potential translation into a clinical setting.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge Al-Mustaqbal University, Faculty of Pharmacy, and Al-Esraa University, Faculty of Pharmacy, for offering the resources obligatory to accomplish this project.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

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The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: ICCMGR2025-020.

The research was licensed approved by the Institutional Review Board of the College of Pharmacy at Al-Esraa University with IRB no. ICCMGR2025-020.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

This investigation was self-funded and received no external financial support.

Author contributions

Ali Jihad Hemid Al-Athari: Conceptualization, methodology design, data validation and critical review of the manuscript. Elaf Mahmood Shihab: Contribution to experimental performance, data acquisition, histopathological analysis and writing an initial draft of the manuscript. Ahmed Khalid Al-Dhalimi: Literature review; data collecting; writing the contributions to discussion and final proofing. Rana Jawad Hasan AlBairmani: Data analysis, statistics, figures preparation and manuscript revision. Samer Salim Shahooth: Resources, dermatological expertise, interpretation of result, and critical manuscript review. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability

The results obtained in the current research are available from the corresponding author upon appropriate request.

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